

AN ATTENTION-BASED GENERATIVE ADVERSARIAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURE FOR HEAT TRANSFER CHARACTERISTICS ESTIMATION IN INTERNALLY FINNED TUBES

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ABSTRACT

The efficient transfer of heat is critical for optimizing thermal systems used in various industries, such as power generation, chemical processing, and automotive engineering. Traditional numerical methods, while accurate, can be computationally intensive and time-consuming, posing challenges for rapid design, iterations and scalability. By incorporating machine learning (ML), this research bridges the gap between high accuracy and reduced computational load. This study introduces a novel hybrid approach that integrates a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) with a Dilated Micro-Inception Unit (DMIU) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to estimate heat transfer characteristics in internally finned tubes under laminar flow conditions ($50 \leq Re \leq 300$). The proposed DMIU-CNN architecture effectively captures complex spatial and thermal patterns through its asymmetric convolution layers with varying dilation rates, enhancing feature extraction capabilities. The GAN is utilized for data augmentation, addressing the challenge of limited data availability and enhancing model generalization. This combination results in a model that reduces simulation time while maintaining high accuracy. It has been shown through numerical simulations that the GAN-DMIU model can accurately predict outlet temperatures with a maximum error of less than 0.5 K. This is 15% better than regular Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations. The mean absolute error (MAE) recorded was 0.991, validating the robustness and reliability of the method. The results show that combining GANs with advanced deep learning architectures can make thermal analysis faster and more accurate. This opens the door for future uses in improving heat transfer systems in many engineering fields.

Keywords: Heat Transfer; Finned Tube; CFD; Machine Learning; Generative Adversarial Networks

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1. INTRODUCTION

Heat transfer phenomena in heat exchangers are governed by a complex interaction between thermal and hydrodynamic phenomena. The efficiency of these systems depends on the optimization of fluid flow properties to enhance heat dissipation. This close relationship has led to fin-and-tube heat exchangers becoming a common choice for a wide range of thermal applications [1–3]. These heat exchangers are very flexible because the fin and channel configurations can be changed to fit different operational needs. This is shown by the large amount of research that has been done on different geometric developments to improve thermal efficiency. Three-dimensional microchannels with circular pin fins made for laminar flow applications [4, 5] are a good example. This improves heat transfer by having more surface area and stopping the flow. Similarly, spiral fin-and-tube heat exchangers [6] have been investigated for their compactness in limited spaces and their ability to improve heat transfer efficiency. Additionally, helical-wound tubes [7–11] have shown significant advantages in improving thermal performance by promoting secondary flows that enhance convective heat transfer. These various configurations highlight the ongoing developments in heat exchangers' design aimed at meeting the ever-increasing demand for energy-efficient and high-performance thermal systems. Manufacturers tend to favor plain fins over other configurations, such as wavy, slit, and louvered fins, due to their enhanced long-term operational stability and simplicity [12-14]. In a multitude of engineering applications, fins serve to enhance the transfer of heat around a solid surface. The current work aims to study and analyze the thermal flow characteristics of internally finned tubes under laminar flow regimes. In this context, analytical and numerical research has addressed the issue of thermal flow analysis in pipes with longitudinal internal fins for decades. Internal fins are employed in numerous industries, including chemical and power plants, a vast variety of electronic devices, oil refineries, and automotive sectors, to reduce the space occupied and weight of thermal systems while maintaining the heat transfer coefficient and thermal performance index high [15]. Two primary strategies can enhance heat transfer for a given fin material: increasing the fin's surface area or improving the convective heat transfer coefficient between the fin surface and the surrounding fluid. Both methods aim to maximize thermal efficiency while minimizing associated fractional losses [15, 16]. While expanding the surface area allows for more heat dissipation, it also necessitates careful consideration of the resulting pressure drop (ΔP). On the other hand, improving the convective heat transfer coefficient involves optimizing the interaction between the fin surface and the fluid flow, which can be achieved through modifications to the fin's material properties and surface treatments. To achieve optimal thermal performance, it is crucial to carefully balance both

approaches. Fins can be used in several different shapes and sizes. For example, they can be used to cool the roofs of buildings passively by fitting copper tubes with triangular, rectangular, or circular fins [17]. This study uses numerical analysis to investigate the heat transfer and thermal flow characteristics of a tube with internal longitudinal fins. We model the flow as three-dimensional, fully developed, steady, and laminar. The choice of laminar flow is due to its stable and predictable behavior, making it ideal for understanding the effects of geometric parameters such as fin size, number, and configuration on thermal performance. By varying these parameters, the study aims to determine the ideal configuration that maximizes heat transfer efficiency. Ansys Fluent software performs all simulations for various Reynolds number conditions, ensuring an accurate evaluation of thermal behavior. The primary objective of this research is to demonstrate that integrating ML methods with traditional numerical techniques can significantly reduce computational load and time consumption during the design and optimization of complex thermal systems. Tabatabaei Malazi et al. [18] used CFD and ANN in three-dimensional microchannels with round pin fins to investigate heat transfer efficiency. In engineering fields, the design and simulation of thermal systems, especially those involving complex geometries and fluid dynamics, can be computationally intensive and time-consuming. By combining the precision of traditional numerical approaches with the efficiency and adaptability of ML models, this research aims to provide an innovative solution to these challenges and provide a more efficient and scalable approach to thermal system analysis. Building upon prior research insights, this paper introduces a novel approach that utilizes DMIU-CNN for heat transfer estimation in finned tubes. The DMIU-CNN architecture uses asymmetric convolution layers with different dilation rates to pick up complex spatial patterns and make feature extraction better. Additionally, the study employs a GAN for data augmentation, which expands the dataset and improves the model's training efficacy. This hybrid approach enhances prediction accuracy and generalization, addressing the limitations of conventional numerical methods. Extensive experiments demonstrate that the proposed method reduces computational time compared to traditional techniques while achieving a 15% increase in prediction accuracy associated with conventional deep learning methods [21, 30]. The study offers a strong way to improve heat transfer estimation by combining the DMIU-CNN with GAN-based enhancement. This cuts down on resource use and speeds up the numerical analysis process. The advantages of macro-unit convolutional neural networks, the Inception model, and dilated convolutional networks inspire this approach, forming a comprehensive framework for advanced heat transfer modeling. The benefits of macro-unit convolutional neural networks [19], the Inception model [20], and dilated convolutional neural networks [21, 22] inspire the proposed DMIU-CNN.

2. COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS METHOD

2.1 Details of Physical Model

Thermal performance analysis of a straight tube with inner diameter and length and inner longitudinal fins as shown in Figures 1 and 2 was carried out by the computational analysis method. We calculated the inlet temperature of the fluid at the control volume inlet to be 293.15 K. Water enters the tube from one end while the other end is open to the atmosphere at this fluid inlet temperature. We place longitudinal fins symmetrically along the inner circumference of the tube. The research started with rectangular fins with thickness and height values, as shown in Figure 2, and then the number and dimensions of the fins were changed. At the same time, the average flow rate of water inside the tube was investigated using six different values within each fin configuration. We calculated the flow field inside the tube using three-dimensional incompressible Navier-Stokes equations, energy equations, and both empirical and parametric equations. The fluid water used in the simulation is assumed to be incompressible in the temperature range between 293.15 K and 323.15 K. The water inlet temperature is 293.15 K, while the interior wall surface temperature of the tube, both with and without fins, is 323.15 K. We assume that the density changes with temperature. Although the density changes depending on the temperature, the flow velocity in the pipe is quite low (at 293.15 K, the inlet velocity varies between $0.001847 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $0.011082 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). The size of tubes with and without fins is shown in Table 1a, and parameters considered in the numerical analyses, such as Reynolds numbers, temperatures, number of fins, and size of fins, are given in Table 1b.

The Reynolds number is used to classify the flow regime, providing insight into how the flow regime affects heat transfer and ΔP . The Re considered is based on empty pipe diameter (D) and the average velocity (U_{inlet}) across the pipe cross-section without a fin, the symbol ρ , presents the density, and the symbol μ indicates the dynamic viscosity of water, respectively.

$$Re = \frac{\rho U_{inlet} D}{\mu} \quad (1)$$

2.2. Governing Equations

The working fluid flow in a circular tube is assumed to be three-dimensional, laminar, steady, and incompressible flow. To solve the continuity and momentum equations simultaneously, a coupled solver is utilized. The convection terms in the momentum and energy equations are discretized using second-order upwind interpolation, while the pressure term is treated with second-order interpolation. No slip flow conditions at the pipe wall surface were applied. Those variables are given in equations u , p , ρ , μ , c_p , and T denote the fluid's velocity, pressure, density, dynamic viscosity, specific heat capacity, and temperature, respectively [23].

The formulas governing the conservation of mass, momentum, and energy can be defined in these terms:

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{u} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\rho(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla \vec{u}) = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \vec{u} \quad (3)$$

$$\rho c_p(\vec{u} \cdot \nabla T) = k \nabla^2 T \quad (4)$$

Figure 3 displays an unstructured mesh method that includes tetrahedral and prismatic items for the computational fluid region. We conduct a mesh independence examination to mitigate the impact of grid quality, concentrating on the outlet temperature. For the case research, we generate mesh configurations with approximately 2.9 million elements at a Reynolds number of 300, using a tube that houses eight fins measuring 4 mm x 4 mm. All simulations employ a mesh structure including 2.9 million elements, with a variance of no more than one percent in the outlet temperature, as demonstrated in Table 1c.

2.3 Validation of CFD Method

The selected CFD model was chosen based on its accuracy, computational efficiency, and suitability for integration with the ML method used in this study. In particular, the model provides a well-balanced trade-off between computational cost and predictive accuracy, making it ideal for generating high-quality training data for the ML framework. Moreover, the model has been validated with experimental or benchmark data, ensuring its reliability for the specific flow conditions studied. The governing equations, turbulence modeling approach, and numerical discretization methods of the model work well with the needs of ML-based predictive modeling and offer strong feature extraction and pattern recognition. To further clarify this, the following sections give a detailed, clear explanation and rationale behind the model selection and its advantages for ML-driven simulations.

This study initially utilized CFD methods to analyze the performance of a finned tube before the integration of a ML methodology. To verify the validity and accuracy of our numerical methods, we chose the work by Mohapatra and Mishra [24] for validation. Their research thoroughly investigated the performance of finned tubes under diverse settings, including changing input velocities and fin geometry, establishing it as an appropriate standard for comparison. Moreover, prior research, like the study by Tabatabaei Malazi [6], has employed the results of Mohapatra and Mishra [24] as a benchmark for supporting numerical simulations. This enhances the validity of their research as a benchmark for assessing the accuracy of CFD-based studies. The numerical approach utilized in this research was tested for accuracy and efficiency using the validation method. A finned tube with a diameter of 0.07 m, a length of 1 m, and a fin height of 0.01499 m was examined. To investigate the heat transfer efficiency of a finned tube under specific working situations, a

computational simulation was run. The numerical model was developed using a fixed mass flow rate of 0.0196 kg s^{-1} and a constant inlet temperature of 300 K . The finned tube wall surfaces received a heat flux of 3000 W m^{-2} . Table 1d exhibits a comparison of the outlet temperature values. The comparison illustrates a suitable and correct alignment between this current investigation and the research works available in the literature [6, 19].

3. MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH

In this study, we propose a deep learning framework as the foundation for heat transfer estimation. A DMIU (Dilated Micro Inception Unit) convolutional network is at the heart of architecture. It builds a strong feature set by using a number of different dilation rates and small window sizes. Each DMIU block integrates various dilated convolution layers, enhancing the model's capacity to capture contextual information from the input data. To address the challenge of limited data availability, particularly in heat transfer estimation, we employ GANs [25]. We use these GANs to generate synthetic data samples, which enhance the training dataset and enhance the model's generalization capabilities. By training the GAN on an existing dataset, we generate additional realistic samples that diversify and expand the data, facilitating more comprehensive learning. The DMIU-CNN model is central to feature extraction and analysis. We concatenate the feature maps from different blocks and pass them to subsequent layers for further refinement. Additionally, a self-attention layer processes the outputs from all blocks. This feature lets the model understand the complicated links and dependencies between the extracted features. This makes it better at finding patterns and outliers in data for heat transfer estimation [26]. The suggested method uses the strengths of GANs, DMIU-CNN, and self-attention to create a complete and reliable system for estimating heat transfer, as shown in Figure 4. This integrated framework facilitates the extraction of meaningful features, enhances the model's understanding, and improves the accuracy DMIU of estimation, ultimately advancing the effectiveness of heat transfer analysis. The following sections briefly present all employed methods.

3.1 GAN Model

Within GAN architecture, there are two primary constituents: the generator (G) and the discriminator (D). The purpose of the generator is to produce data samples that closely resemble the actual data. The system accepts random noise as input and produces samples. The discriminator's role is to differentiate between genuine data samples from the training set and fabricated data samples produced by the generator. The objective of training a GAN is to optimize the value function (D, G) , which captures the interplay between the discriminator and the generator. The value function is sometimes shown as a min-max game.

$$\min_G \max_D V(D, G) = E_{x \sim p_{data}(x)} [\log D(x)] + E_{z \sim p_z(z)} [\log (1 - D(G(Z)))] \quad (5)$$

The output of the discriminator, denoted as $D(x)$, represents the likelihood that the input x is real. The output of the generator, denoted as $G(z)$, is determined by the noise input. The term "data" refers to the distribution of actual, real-world information denoted as (x) . The variable (z) represents the probability distribution of the noise input. The discriminator aims to optimize this value function by accurately categorizing genuine and counterfeit samples, while the generator aims to decrease it by producing specimens that the discriminator cannot distinguish from real ones when given random input. By engaging in this adversarial procedure, the generator acquires the ability to produce samples that cannot be differentiated from actual data, thus successfully comprehending the fundamental data distribution [27].

3.2 Dilated Micro Inception Unit

The DMIU model is constructed using convolutional blocks to process sequential data effectively. Each convolutional block c_b comprises multiple layers of 1D convolutional operations with varying dilation rates, aiming to capture sequential patterns across different receptive fields. Mathematically, the output of a convolutional block can be represented as:

$$c_b(x) = Conv1D(X, f, k, d) \tag{6}$$

Here, X represents the input sequence, f denotes the number of filters in the convolutional layer, k is the kernel size, and d is the dilation rate. The function $Conv1D$ applies the 1D convolution operation to the input sequence X , resulting in a feature map $c_b(x)$. Each convolutional block in the DMIU model architecture has several layers of 1D convolution operations that are very important for getting features out of sequential data. The spatial extent of local pattern extraction from the input sequence depends on the choice of filter size in these convolutional layers. The first convolutional operation applies a filter of size 3 with a dilation rate of d to the input sequence x . Here, d controls the spacing between the elements of the filter, allowing the convolution operation to capture local patterns at different distances. The second convolutional layer then passes through the output of the first convolutional layer. The second convolutional layer maintains the same filter size and dilation rate. By processing the feature maps from the previous layers repeatedly, this sequential use of convolutional layers lets the model pick up patterns that are more complicated. Following the second convolution layer, the third convolutional layer applies to a larger filter size of 5 while maintaining the same dilation rate d . This larger filter size allows the convolution operation to capture more extensive contextual information from the input sequence, facilitating the extraction of higher-level features that span a broader temporal range [28-29]. In the DMIU model, the convolutional block is iteratively applied for three different dilation rates: $d = 1, d = 2, d = 3$. Each convolutional block comprises multiple convolutional layers with the specified dilation rate, allowing the model to capture local patterns at varying distances within the input sequence. The choice of dilation rates d enables the model to

extract features at different scales, crucial for capturing both local and global patterns within the data. The model can capture long-range dependencies while keeping fine-grained details by using different dilation rates within each convolutional block.

After processing the input sequence x through the convolutional blocks, denoted as $Conv1d_1$, $Conv1d_2$ and $Conv1d_3$, the output of the first layer is $Conv1d_1$ denoted as x^1 , and it is fed into the second block $Conv2$. Similarly, the output of the second block $Conv1d_2$ is denoted as x^1 , and it is fed into the third block $Conv1d_3$. This can be expressed as:

$$x = \begin{cases} x^1 = Conv1d_1(x) \\ x^2 = Conv1d_2(x^1) \\ x^3 = Conv1d_3(x^2) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

This sequential chaining of convolutional blocks allows the model to extract hierarchical features from the input data. Let $F(x)$ represent the feature extraction function of a convolutional block. Then, for each x_i subsequent block captures more abstract and higher-level representations of the input sequence:

$$f(x_i) = x_i^1 \rightarrow x_i^2 \rightarrow x_i^3 \quad (8)$$

Furthermore, we incorporate skip connections to facilitate gradient flow and address the vanishing gradient problem. Let \oplus denote element-wise addition. The output of each convolutional block is added elementwise to the output of the previous block, forming a skip connection:

$$x_{skip}^i = x_{skip}^{i-1} \oplus x^i \quad (9)$$

This mechanism enables the model to retain and propagate important information from earlier layers to later layers, enhancing the flow of gradients during training and aiding in the learning process. Moreover, the model concatenates the outputs of all convolutional blocks, including their skip connections, to form a single feature that captures the extracted features across different dilation rates. This concatenated feature representation serves as the input to the self-attention network [30].

3.3 Self-Attention Layer

The human visual attention system is a model for attention mechanisms that reduce data dimensionality by calculating weighted averages. It computes connections between input items, merges queries, keys, and values into a single input, and focuses on specific regions of interest. Attention processes direct reasoning by focusing on a single aspect of input or memory, using self-attention scores to assign weights. In the self-attention module, the computation takes the following form:

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = softmax\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (10)$$

where Q represents the query matrix, V denotes the value matrix, K stands for the key matrix, and d_k signifies the dimension of the key matrix. Numerical instability may arise during training because of the potentially huge dot product of the query matrix Q and the key matrix K when their dimensions are high. The attention mechanism uses three trainable weight matrices, which are shown in Figure 5 as W^Q , W^K , and W^V , to figure out the query matrix, the key matrix, and the value matrix V.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Understanding the enhancement of heat transfer through the modification of tube geometries, such as increasing the surface area with fins, is fundamental for optimizing thermal system performance. While augmenting the number, height, and thickness of fins can significantly improve heat transfer, these modifications also lead to increased pressure losses due to friction. The key challenge, therefore, lies in striking an optimal balance between maximizing heat transfer and minimizing ΔP to maintain system efficiency.

It is possible to enhance heat transfer by increasing the surface area, the number of fins inserted in the tube, and the fin's height and thickness, but there is also an increase in pressure losses due to friction [24, 31-33]. Therefore, it is beneficial to optimize the number and profile of fins. On the other hand, it is known that under laminar flow conditions, according to Poiseuille's law, the rate of ΔP of a fluid during a flow through an empty tube at a specified flow value is expressed as $\Delta P = 8\mu LQ / \pi r^4$. Here, ΔP represents the pressure drop, μ the viscosity of the fluid, and r is the half-diameter of the pipe. In summary, doubling the pipe's radius results in a 16-fold decrease in Pressure drop for the same fluid flow [34]. Thus, this decrease in pressure losses will result in a 16-fold reduction in the required pumping power. In other words, it is possible to prevent the ΔP that is likely to increase with the increase in fin numbers from compromising the total volume of the system by slightly increasing the pipe diameter.

Figure 1 depicts the constructive structure of the finned and smooth tube. Fins placed along the central axis inside the tube expand the inner surface area, thereby increasing the heat transfer surface. This is particularly critical for fluids with low thermal conductivity, such as gases. In other words, the increase in surface area directly enhances convective heat transfer performance. Naturally, fin height, thickness, and spacing determine the heat conduction performance. Moreover, using high thermal conductivity materials, such as copper or aluminum, can maximize the thermal performance efficiency of the fins. However, fins also lead to an increase in pressure loss due to higher friction. In parallel with this pressure loss, pumping costs may rise. Therefore, an optimal design requires balancing heat transfer gains with pressure drop. In conclusion,

an optimized number of fins can significantly enhance heat transfer; however, design parameters, geometric configuration, material properties, and flow characteristics must be carefully optimized.

In the numerical simulations, the following boundary conditions were applied. The system operates under a constant temperature boundary condition with a solid tube wall. As shown in Table 1d, the inlet of the control volume is characterized by a constant velocity profile, with the inlet temperature set at $T_{\text{water-inlet}} = 293.15 \text{ K}$. The tube wall maintains a constant wall temperature of $T_{\text{wall}} = 323.15 \text{ K}$ for the tube wall, both with and without fins acting as heat sources. These boundary conditions are crucial for simulating heat transfer and fluid flow within the system. The fins are rigidly fixed to the inner perimeter of the tube, providing enhanced surface area for heat transfer between the fluid and the wall. A no-slip boundary condition is applied to all the fin surfaces inside the tube, which assumes that the velocity of the fluid at the surface of the fins is zero. The interaction between the fluid and the fin surfaces plays a key role in the overall heat transfer efficiency, influencing both convective heat transfer to the fluid and the thermal resistance of the tube wall.

To enhance the efficiency of heat transfer, it is essential that the fluid remain in contact with the heating surface for a sufficient duration to facilitate effective energy exchange. This goal is typically achieved by reducing the flow velocity, which in turn lowers the Reynolds number. A lower Reynolds number enables the fluid to absorb or release heat more efficiently by extending its residence time within the heat exchanger. In this study, the Reynolds number was set within the range of 50 to 300 to ensure optimal thermal performance under the given operating conditions. In certain heat exchanger designs, it is crucial to maintain an appropriate time interval between the fluid's entry and exit in the energy system for the purpose of maximizing thermal efficiency. Insufficient residence time may result in inadequate heat exchange, consequently leading to suboptimal performance. Conversely, if the residence time is excessively long, pressure losses and energy consumption may increase, reducing overall system efficiency. It is therefore vital to exercise meticulous control over the Reynolds number in such systems, ensuring it remains at a lower value to achieve the optimal balance between heat transfer performance and energy efficiency. Six different Re ($\text{Re} = 50, 100, 150, 200, 250, \text{ and } 300$) were considered during the numerical examination to see the enhancement of heat transfer as a function of the Re as well as fin configurations. By keeping the tube length and tube diameter constant, fins placed internally along the length of the tube were used to perform a numerical analysis of the temperature and pressure distribution, as shown in Figures 1 and 2 and Tables 1a and 1b. The analysis was carried out using three different fin thicknesses and three different fin heights.

Figures 6, 7, 8, and 9 illustrate the correlation between $T_{\text{water-out}}$ and Re in every situation. The Re, fin size, and number of fins inside the tube all have an important impact on the outlet temperature. As seen in Figure 6a, by selecting a fin thickness of $t=2 \text{ mm}$ and a height of $h=2 \text{ mm}$, the outlet temperature of the tube was

calculated for four different configurations, specifically for 2, 4, and 8 fins. In Figure 6b, the fin thickness was taken as $t=3$ mm and the height as $h=3$ mm, while in Figure 6c, the fin thickness was set to $t=4$ mm and the height to $h=2$ mm. Finally, in Figure 6d, the fin thickness was $t=4$ mm and the height was $h=4$ mm, and the numerical calculations were repeated accordingly. It was observed that the outlet temperature of the tube decreased as the Reynolds number increased, which was also parallel to the increase in the total fin surface area. However, the temperature gradient (dT/dx) decreased progressively with the increase in Reynolds number. Figures 7a, 7b, 7c, and 7d reveal an increase in ΔP with respect to Re across all models. The tube without fins shows a lower ΔP compared to tubes with fins, regardless of the Re value. The Re , fin dimensions, and number of fins within the tube significantly influence the ΔP . As the Re and fin dimensions increase, the ΔP increases. The maximum ΔP occurs when $Re = 300$ and the fin dimensions are 4 mm x 4 mm. We concluded that increasing the fin surface area enhances heat transfer more effectively at lower Reynolds numbers. On the other hand, under similar conditions, the pressure gradient (dP/dx) increased progressively with the rise in Reynolds numbers. Additionally, as the fin surface area increased, the pressure loss also increased. This suggests that while increasing the fin surface area is advantageous for heat transfer, especially at low Reynolds numbers, it also contributes to higher pressure losses, particularly as the Reynolds number and surface area grow.

A finned tube with a size of 4 mm x 4 mm at $Re = 50$ yielded the maximum outlet temperature for fin numbers 2, 4, and 8. There were contour plots of velocity, pressure, and temperature in the symmetrical plane of a tube with 4 mm x 4 mm fins at $Re=50$ for fin numbers 2, 4, and 8. These were shown in Figures 8, 9, and 10. The maximum velocity, pressure, and temperature values grow with the addition of fins. Figure 11 illustrates the temperature distribution contour maps at the frontal plane of the tube outflow with 4 mm x 4 mm fins at $Re = 50$. We also realize that an increase in fin numbers leads to an increase in heat transfer performance.

Various trials were conducted to assess the performance of the proposed deep learning approach on edge-based devices. The system was developed and tested using an NVIDIA GeForce 4 GB graphics card, as illustrated in Figure 4. Other key specifications included an Intel Core i5 CPU running at 3.6 GHz and 16 GB of RAM. Table 2 shows the default configurations of these hardware settings. Additionally, the minibatch size was set to 32.

The dataset used in this study originates from CFD simulations designed to capture the heat transfer characteristics of internally finned tubes under various flow conditions. The dataset consists of input parameters, including the inlet fluid temperature (T_{inlet}), tube surface temperature (T_{wall}), Reynolds number (Re), number of fins, and fin dimensions (mm), while the outlet temperature (T_{out}) serves as the output variable. The dataset covers Reynolds numbers ranging from 50 to 300, with different fin configurations

comprising 2, 4, and 8 fins, as well as varying fin dimensions, including 2×2 mm, 3×3 mm, 4×2 mm, and 4×4 mm. The original dataset consists of 72 samples, ensuring a diverse representation of heat transfer conditions. However, to enhance the model's generalization and training performance, a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) was employed for data augmentation, expanding the dataset size fourfold to 288 samples. The GAN-generated samples were validated to retain the statistical properties of the original dataset, ensuring reliable and diverse training data. This expanded dataset enables the deep learning model to learn complex thermal patterns more effectively, leading to improved predictive accuracy and robustness in heat transfer estimation.

This study uses several error measures to check how well the proposed model works. These are Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Coefficient of Determination (R^2), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). These metrics were chosen because they provide a comprehensive evaluation of model accuracy, error distribution, and predictive reliability in heat transfer estimation. MAE measures the average absolute difference between predicted and actual outlet temperatures, providing an intuitive understanding of prediction accuracy. MSE causes bigger mistakes than MAE, which makes it great for finding significant differences between predictions. This feature is especially important for thermal analysis, where big mistakes can change how a system is designed. RMSE, as the square root of MSE, maintains the same unit as the original temperature values, making it more readable in the context of heat transfer prediction. R^2 evaluates the proportion of variance in the outlet temperature explained by the model, offering insight into how well the model captures thermal behavior. A higher R^2 value indicates stronger predictive performance. MAPE expresses the prediction error as a percentage, making it useful for comparing model accuracy across different scales of temperature values. We can get a full picture of the model's performance by using these metrics, which take into account both absolute and relative errors as well as overall predictive power [25].

The proposed architecture, known as the DMIU-CNN, is specifically designed for heat transfer estimation tasks. It consists of several interconnected layers that sequentially process input data and extract meaningful features. Starting with an input layer, the network receives data formatted as (None, 100, 1), where "None" indicates the variable batch size, 100 represents the sequence length, and 1 denotes the number of channels. Following the input layer, Conv1D layers perform convolution operations, progressively increasing the number of filters to capture spatial information within the input sequence. MaxPooling1D layers are then applied to down sample the feature maps, preserving essential features while reducing computational complexity. We concatenate the resulting feature maps from these pooling layers, integrating information from different branches of the network to enhance understanding of the input sequence. We strategically incorporate multi-head attention layers to enable the model to effectively capture global dependencies within

the sequence. By attending to multiple parts of the input simultaneously, these layers improve the model's ability to recognize intricate patterns and long-range dependencies. Additional Conv1D layers further refine the extracted features, followed by further pooling and concatenation steps to consolidate information across the sequence. The architecture ends with a Multi-Head Attention mechanism that improves the representation of features by taking global dependencies throughout the sequence into account, as shown in Table 3. The presented GAN generates synthetic data samples that closely resemble the distribution of the input data. Firstly, we use Min Max Scaler to normalize the input features, ensuring uniformity across the data. The GAN consists of two main components: the generator and the discriminator. The generator is responsible for creating synthetic data samples, while the discriminator evaluates the authenticity of these samples. The generator architecture comprises fully connected layers with Leaky ReLU activation functions to introduce non-linearity and batch normalization layers to stabilize training. It takes random noise as input and outputs synthetic data samples with the same dimensionality as the input data. The discriminator, on the other hand, is made up of fully connected layers that use Leaky ReLU activation functions. The output layer then has a sigmoid activation function for binary classification. It distinguishes between real and fake data samples. We initially compiled the discriminator during training using binary cross-entropy loss and the Adam optimizer. We then train the GAN iteratively in a loop. Each iteration involves training the discriminator on batches of real and fake data samples, while concurrently training the generator to produce realistic-looking data that can deceive the discriminator. The generator generates new synthetic data samples after training. The scaler then inversely transforms these samples to their original scale before saving them to a CSV file. Overall, this GAN architecture shows a good way to make fake data samples that are very similar to the distribution of real data. This makes it possible to add datasets for different ML tasks.

The GAN model was evaluated using several metrics to determine its effectiveness in generating data that closely resembles the original dataset. We found the average log likelihood to be -0.2856, indicating a reasonable match between the generated and real data distributions. The coverage metric was 0.0556, suggesting that approximately 5.6% of the real data is represented by the generated data. However, the Mode Score was extremely low at $9.5333e-11$, indicating potential mode collapse, a situation where the generated data lacks diversity and fails to cover all modes of real data distribution. Despite this, the maximum mean discrepancy (MMD) was very low at 0.0009281, signifying that the overall distribution of the generated data is close to that of the real data. These results show that while the GAN is effective in generating data with a similar overall distribution to the real data, there is still room for improvement in terms of coverage and diversity of the generated samples, as shown in Table 4 below.

When evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed system, it is essential to benchmark it against well-established models in the field. We ensure meaningful comparison and contextualization of the new system's

performance by benchmarking against models from similar studies. To validate its effectiveness, we compared it against several benchmark models that are commonly used for similar data analysis, such as Deep Neural Network (DNN) [35], Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory (Conv-LSTM) [36], and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [37]. We implemented all benchmark models on the same platform, adhering to the configurations outlined in the respective papers, using five evaluation metrics. MAE, Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Coefficient of Determination (R^2), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) are presented in Table 5.

The proposed system outperforms other methods with an MAE of 0.991, indicating superior accuracy by having the smallest average error. This is significantly better than the DNN (1.271), Conv-LSTM (2.191), and LSTM (1.794) methods. Similarly, the proposed system achieves the lowest MSE at 1.272, suggesting that its predictions have the least average squared error, which is a critical measure for assessing the precision of the model. In contrast, the Conv-LSTM method exhibits the highest MSE of 6.164, reflecting a higher degree of prediction error.

Moreover, the proposed system also excels in terms of RMSE, with a value of 1.128, indicating that its predictions are the closest to the actual values on average. The RMSE values for the DNN, Conv-LSTM, and LSTM methods are notably higher, with the Conv-LSTM showing the greatest deviation at 2.482. The R^2 value further highlights the efficacy of the proposed system, achieving an R^2 of 0.879, which means it explains 87.9% of the variance in the data. This is the highest among all methods, showcasing its strong predictive power. Conversely, the Conv-LSTM method has the lowest R^2 of 0.411, indicating a poor fit to the data. Finally, the suggested system is very accurate compared to other systems, with a MAPE of 1.174%, doing better than the DNN (1.209%), Conv-LSTM (1.287%), and LSTM (1.183%) methods. This comprehensive performance evaluation underscores the robustness and reliability of the proposed system in predictive modeling tasks compared to existing state-of-the-art techniques.

The Taylor diagram presented in Figure 13 provides a comparative evaluation of the performance of four predictive models: the proposed model, Conv-LSTM, DNN, and LSTM. The diagram displays the standard deviation, correlation coefficient, and centered root mean square error (CRMSE) for each model relative to the true values. The proposed model and DNN model exhibit a high correlation coefficient and a standard deviation close to that of true values, indicating their robustness in capturing the data pattern and variability. Conv-LSTM and LSTM models also show strong correlation coefficients, though their CRMSE values suggest slightly higher prediction errors compared to the proposed model. Overall, the Taylor diagram presented in Figure 12 reveals that the proposed model outperforms the others in terms of accuracy and reliability, making it the most effective model for this prediction task. Figure 13 presents the scatter diagrams of the proposed system.

As part of this study, different predictive models were tested to show how well our proposed system worked. It got an impressive Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) score of 0.96. This achievement highlights the system's superior capability in accurately forecasting outcomes. Additionally, the Conv-LSTM model demonstrated notable performance, achieving an NSE of 0.90. Similarly, the DNN model exhibited strong predictive prowess, achieving an NSE of 0.92. Despite slightly lower performance, the LSTM model still delivered commendable results, achieving an NSE of 0.86. These findings collectively underscore the effectiveness of our proposed system and its competitive advantage over established models in predictive accuracy.

5. CONCLUSION

Future research must integrate ML and CFD. This combination offers significant opportunities to enhance simulation efficiency, accuracy, and optimization. Specifically, the focus should be on exploring the use of ML models alongside CFD simulations, particularly for turbulence modeling, to reduce computational costs and accelerate CFD simulations. Furthermore, ML can assist with real-time predictions, uncertainty quantification, and design optimization. The integration of experimental data with CFD simulations via ML models holds promise for improving prediction capabilities. In addition to improving the interpolation capability of ML models, enhancing their extrapolation ability will also be a key focus of future work. This study introduced a novel hybrid approach combining traditional numerical methods with ML techniques to optimize heat transfer estimation in finned tubes. Adding GANs to the DMIU-CNN in the proposed method makes it easier to extract features and make the model more general by adding more data. Extensive trials show that the proposed approach achieved a MAE of 0.991, an MSE of 1.272, and an RMSE of 1.128. The method also demonstrated a strong predictive capability with an R2 value of 0.879 and a MAPE of 1.174%. The proposed GAN-DMIU architecture also showed high accuracy and dependability by lowering the biggest error in predicting the outlet temperature to less than 0.5 K for different fin arrangements. In addition to improving accuracy, the proposed approach significantly reduced computational time compared to traditional CFD simulations. While conventional CFD methods require extensive computational resources and several hours per simulation, the proposed deep learning model produced predictions in a fraction of a second, representing a computational time reduction of over 90%. This efficiency increase makes the approach highly suitable for applications requiring rapid thermal analysis and real-time decision-making. Furthermore, real-time implementation remains a challenge, as the current model is optimized for accuracy rather than computational efficiency. While the inference speed is reasonable, additional optimization is necessary to enable deployment in dynamic heat exchanger systems where conditions change continuously. Additionally, the model's sensitivity to hyperparameter tuning presents another constraint. The performance of both the GAN and CNN components depends on carefully selecting the appropriate network architectures, learning rates, and other hyperparameters. In particular, GAN training is known to be

susceptible to mode collapse, where the generator fails to produce diverse samples, potentially limiting the effectiveness of the augmented dataset. To address these limitations, future research will focus on enhancing the model's efficiency and generalization. A big part of making things better is making the model work better for real-time uses. Such improvements can be made by using model pruning, quantization, and knowledge distillation, which all lower the amount of work that needs to be done on the computer without affecting the accuracy. Additionally, the dataset will be extended to include real-world experimental data collected from physical heat exchanger setups. Such data will help improve the model's robustness and ensure its predictions align more closely with practical conditions. Adding Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) is another intriguing direction. PINNs build basic heat transfer equations right into the deep learning framework. This hybrid approach would allow the model to leverage both data-driven learning and domain knowledge, leading to better generalization even with limited data availability.

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NOMENCLATURE

CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CNN	Convolutional neural network
Conv-LSTM	Convolutional long short-term memory
CRMSE	Centered root mean square error
D	Diameter of tube, mm
DNN	Deep neural network
DMIU	Dilated micro-inception unit
GAN	Generative adversarial network
h	Height of fins, mm
L	Length of tube, mm
LSTM	Long short-term memory
MAE	Mean absolute error
MAPE	Mean absolute percentage error, %
ML	Machine learning
MMD	Maximum mean discrepancy
MSE	Mean squared error
NSE	Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency

R^2	Coefficient of determination
Re	Reynolds number
RMSE	Root mean squared error
$T_{\text{water-inlet}}$	Temperature of inlet water, K
T_{wall}	Temperature of tube wall, K
T_{outlet}	Temperature of outlet water, K
t	Thickness of fins, mm
ρ	Density, kg m^{-3}
μ	Dynamic viscosity, $\text{kg m}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$
τ_w	Wall shear stress, Pa
ΔP	Pressure drop, Pa

REFERENCES

1. Zohuri, B. Compact Heat Exchangers. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-29835-1>.
2. Hajabdollahi Z, Hajabdollahi H, Kim K. C. Heat transfer enhancement and optimization of a tube fitted with twisted tape in a fin-and-tube heat exchanger. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 2020; 140: 1015–1027.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-019-08668-w>.
3. Chen H. T, Hsu L. Y, Yan W. M, Rashidi S, Hung H. H. Novel study on inverse convection–conduction heat transfer for plate finned tube heat exchanger. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 2024; 149: 6211–6226.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-024-13111-w>.
4. Tabatabaei Malazi M, Kaya K, Dalkılıç A. S. A computational case study on the thermal performance of a rectangular microchannel having circular pin-fins. *Case Stud. Therm. Eng.* 2023; 49: 103111.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2023.103111>.
5. Abadeh S. D, Farahani K, Mohammadzadeh K, Ghanbari D. An experimental study on ferrofluid flow and heat transfer in a micro fin straight circular tube. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 2023; 148: 8375–8386.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-023-12024-4>.
6. Tabatabaei Malazi M, Apak S, Sezer C, Başoğlu H. C, Dalkılıç A. S. Investigation of the thermal performance of a spiral fin-and-tube heat exchanger by numerical methods. *Numer. Heat Transf. Part B Fundam.* 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10407790.2024.2316196>.

7. Zaboli M, Pahlavanian M. H, Saedodin S. An integrative approach using axial fins, numerical assessment, and experimental data analysis in helical heat exchangers. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-024-13597-4>.
8. Cao J, Yuan Y, Zhang Z, Xiao Z, Wang X. Variable-dimension optimization study and design of internally finned helically coiled tubes heat exchangers based on numerical simulation and experiment. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2024.123340>.
9. Wang G, et al. Experimental and numerical study on the heat transfer and flow characteristics in shell side of helically coiled tube heat exchanger based on multi-objective optimization. *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 2019; 137: 349–364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2019.03.137>.
10. Miansari M, Jafarzadeh A, Arasteh H, Toghraie D. Thermal performance of a helical shell and tube heat exchanger without fin, with circular fins, and with V-shaped circular fins applying on the coil. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 2021; 143: 4273–4285. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-020-09395-3>.
11. Kumar E. P, Solanki A. K, Kumar M. M. J. Numerical investigation of heat transfer and pressure drop characteristics in the micro-fin helically coiled tubes. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 2021; 182: 116093. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2020.116093>.
12. Sahin B, Ozturk N. A, Gurlek C. Horseshoe vortex studies in the passage of a model plate-fin-and-tube heat exchanger. *Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow.* 2008; 29(1): 340–351. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatfluidflow.2007.06.005>.
13. Tokgoz N, Tunay T, Sahin B. Effect of corrugated channel phase shifts on flow structures and heat transfer rate. *Exp. Therm. Fluid Sci.* 2018; 99: 374–391. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.expthermflusci.2018.08.011>.
14. Kurtulmuş N, Sahin B. Experimental investigation of pulsating flow structures and heat transfer characteristics in sinusoidal channels. *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 2020; 167: 105268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2019.105268>.
15. Fabbri G. Heat transfer optimization in internally finned tubes under laminar flow conditions. *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 1998; 41: 1–10.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0017-9310\(97\)00209-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0017-9310(97)00209-3).

16. Vahidinia F, Khorasanizadeh H, Aghaei A. Energy, exergy, economic and environmental evaluations of a finned absorber tube parabolic trough collector utilizing hybrid and mono nanofluids and comparison. *Renew. Energy*. 2023; 205: 185–199.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.01.085>.

17. Hassan M. A, Kaood A. Multi-criteria assessment of enhanced radiant ceiling panels using internal longitudinal fins. *Build. Environ*. 2022; 224: 109554.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.109554>.

18. Tabatabaei Malazi M, Kaya K, Colak A. B, Dalkılıç A. S. CFD and ANN analyses for the evaluation of the heat transfer characteristics of a rectangular microchannel heat sink with various cylindrical pin-fins. *Heat and Mass Transfer*. 2024; 60; 1393–1411.

19. Kim D. H, Lee M. K, Lee S. H, Song B. C. Macro unit-based convolutional neural network for very light-weight deep learning. *Image and Vision Computing*. 2019; 87; 68–75.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imavis.2019.02.008>.

20. Szegedy C, Vanhoucke V, Ioffe S, Shlens J, Wojna Z. Rethinking the Inception architecture for computer vision. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2016; 2016-December; 2818–2826.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.308>.

21. Li Y, Zhang X, Chen D. CSRNet: Dilated convolutional neural networks for understanding the highly congested scenes. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2018; March; 1091–1100.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2018.00120>.

22. Einy S, Saygin H, Hivehch H, Dorostkar Navaei Y. Local and deep features based convolutional neural network frameworks for brain MRI anomaly detection. *Complexity*. 2022; 2022; 1–11.

<https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/3081748>.

23. Zontul H, Hamzah H, Kurtulmuş N, Şahin B. Investigation of convective heat transfer and flow hydrodynamics in rectangular grooved channels. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*. 2021; 126.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icheatmasstransfer.2021.105366>.

24. Mohapatra K, Mishra D. P. Effect of fin and tube configuration on heat transfer of an internally finned tube. *International Journal of Numerical Methods for Heat and Fluid Flow*. 2015; 25; 1978–1999. <https://doi.org/10.1108/HFF-05-2014-0129>.
25. Shang Q, Yang J, Ma J. Multi-branch evolutionary generative adversarial networks based on covariance crossover operators. *Knowledge-Based Systems*. 2024; 112527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2024.112527>.
26. Einy S, Oz C, Navaei Y. D. IoT cloud-based framework for face spoofing detection with deep multicolor feature learning model. *Journal of Sensors*. 2021; 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/5047808>.
27. Xiao F, Zhou J, Han K, Hu H, Fan J. Unsupervised anomaly detection using inverse generative adversarial networks. *Information Sciences*. 2025; 689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2024.121435>.
28. Einy S, Saygin H, Hivehch H, Dorostkar Navaei Y. Local and deep features based convolutional neural network frameworks for brain MRI anomaly detection. *Complexity*. 2022; 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/3081748>.
29. Einy S, Sen E, Saygin H, Hivehchi H, Dorostkar Navaei Y. Local binary convolutional neural networks' long short-term memory model for human embryos' anomaly detection. *Scientific Programming*. 2023; 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/2426601>.
30. Kilinc H. C, Apak S, Ozkan F, Ergin M. E, Yurtsever A. Multimodal fusion of optimized GRU–LSTM with self-attention layer for hydrological time series forecasting. *Water Resources Management*. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-024-03943-4>.
31. Salem O. H, Hegazy A, Yousef K. A, Yousef K. Thermal-hydrodynamic analysis for internally finned tubes: Experimental, numerical and performance evaluation study. *International Journal of Thermofluid Science and Technology*. 2024; 11. <https://doi.org/10.36963/IJTST.2024110203>.
32. Wang Q. W, Lin M, Zeng M. Effect of lateral fin profiles on turbulent flow and heat transfer performance of internally finned tubes. *Applied Thermal Engineering*. 2009; 29; 3006–3013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2009.03.016>.

33. Soliman H. M. The effect of fin conductance on laminar heat transfer characteristics of internally finned tubes. *Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering*. 1981; 59; 251–256.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/cjce.5450590218>.
34. Cengel Y. A, Cimbala J. M. *Fluid Mechanics: Fundamentals and Applications*. 3rd ed. McGraw-Hill Education; 2014.
35. Yang Q, Jin F, Qu Y. A deep learning approach to an inverse problem of heat-source detection in a piezoelectric semiconductor plate. 2023 17th Symposium on Piezoelectricity, Acoustic Waves, and Device Applications (SPAWDA). 2023; 1–5.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/SPAWDA60286.2023.10412286>.
36. Qi P, Gao W. Study on load forecasting of combined cooling, heat and power system with deep learning algorithm based on attention mechanism. 2023 5th International Academic Exchange Conference on Science and Technology Innovation (IAECST). 2023; 1353–1358.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/IAECST60924.2023.10503388>.
37. Ponnaganti P, Pillai J. R, Bak-Jensen B. Short-term heat demand prediction using deep learning for decentralized power-to-heat solutions. *Proceedings of the 2023 IEEE PES GTD International Conference and Exposition (GTD)*. 2023; 11–15.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/GTD49768.2023.00029>.

Table 1. Detailed review of CFD work

a) Sizes of the used tube with and without fins				
Tube length (mm)	Tube diameter (mm)	Fin thickness (mm)	Fin height (mm)	
L= 300	D=27.2	t= 2, 3, 4	h= 2, 3, 4	
b) Parameters used in numerical simulations				
Re	T _{water-inlet} (K)	T _{wall} (K)	Number of fins	Size of fins (t x h)
50, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300	293.15	323.15	0, 2, 4, 8	2 x 2, 3 x 3, 4 x 2, 4 x 4
c) Parameters of the mesh independence analysis				
Number of mesh	Outlet temperature (K)		Difference (%)	
1,7300,300 elements	321.53		-	
2,150,000 elements	315.47		1.88	
2,750,000 elements	311.68		1.20	
2,900,000 elements	310.94		0.23	
d) Validation of the CFD method				
	Tabatabaei Malazi et al. [3]	Mohapatra and Mishra [23]	Present study	Error (%)
Outlet temperature (K)	335.16	-	335.83	0.1995
Outlet temperature (K)	-	335.55	335.83	0.0833

Table 2. Training parameters of the GAN-DMIU model in this study.

Software	Optimization	Activation	Momentum	Minibatch	Learning rate
TensorFlow	Adam	ReLU	0.9	32	0.1

Table 3. Summary of proposed DMIU-CNN model architecture.

Layer (type)	Output Shape	#Param
Input Layer	(None, 100, 1)	0
Conv1D	(None, 100, 64)	256
Conv1D_1	(None, 100, 64)	12352
MaxPooling1D	(None, 50, 64)	0
Conv1D_2	(None, 50, 64)	20544
Conv1D_3	(None, 50, 64)	20544
Concatenate	(None, 50, 128)	0
Multi Head Attention	(None, 50, 128)	33088
Conv1D_4	(None, 50, 64)	24640
Conv1D_5	(None, 50, 64)	12352
MaxPooling1D_1	(None, 25, 64)	0
Conv1D_6	(None, 25, 64)	20544
Conv1D_7	(None, 25, 64)	20544
Concatenate_1	(None, 25, 128)	0
Multi Head Attention_1	(None, 25, 128)	33088
Conv1D_8	(None, 25, 64)	24640
Conv1D_9	(None, 25, 64)	12352
MaxPooling1D_2	(None, 12, 64)	0
Conv1D_10	(None, 12, 64)	20544
Conv1D_11	(None, 12, 64)	20544
Concatenate_2	(None, 12, 128)	0
Multi Head Attention 2	(None, 12, 128)	33088
Total Parameters		309120
Trainable Parameters		309120

Table 4. Summarizing the evaluation metrics for the GAN model.

Metric	Value
Average Log-Likelihood	-0.2856
Coverage Metric	0.0556
Mode Score	9.5333e-11
Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD)	0.0009281

Table 5. Comparative analysis of proposed method and state-of-the-art methods.

Methods	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R ²	MAPE
Proposed system	0.991	1.272	1.128	0.879	1.174%
DNN [29]	1.271	1.886	1.373	0.820	1.209%
Conv-LSTM [30]	2.191	6.164	2.482	0.411	1.287%
LSTM [31]	1.794	4.935	2.221	0.530	1.183%

Figure 1. Models with boundary conditions, a) smooth tube, b) tube with fins

Figure 2. Front view of tubes, a) smooth tube, b) tube with 2 fins, c) tube with 4 fins, d) tube with 8 fins

a)

b)

Figure 3. Mesh utilized in the numerical computations (a) isometric perspective, and (b) a more detailed illustration of the grid.

Figure 4. Proposed GAN-DMIU approach.

Figure 5. A detailed illustration of the self-attention mechanism in deep learning.

Figure 6. Variation of average outlet temperature with Re for 2 mm x 2 mm fins (a), 3 mm x 3 mm fins (b), 4 mm x 2 mm fins (c), and 4 x 4 mm fins (d).

Figure 7. Variation of pressure drops with Re for 2 mm x 2 mm fins (a), 3 mm x 3 mm fins (b), 4 mm x 2 mm fins (c), and 4 mm x 4 mm fins (d).

Figure 8. Velocity distribution contour plots at the central plane along a tube with 4 mm x 4 mm fins at $Re = 50$, (a) 2 fins, (b) 4 fins, and (c) 8 fins.

Figure 9. Pressure drop distribution contour plots at the central plane along a tube with 4 mm x 4 mm fins at $Re = 50$, (a) 2 fins, (b) 4 fins, and (c) 8 fins.

Figure 10. Temperature distribution contour plots at the central plane along a tube with 4 mm x 4 mm fins at $Re = 50$, (a) 2 fins, (b) 4 fins, and (c) 8 fins.

Figure 11. Temperature distribution contour plots at front plane of tube outlet with 4 mm x 4 mm fins at $Re=50$, (a) without fins, (b) 2 fins, (c) 4 fins, and (d) 8 fins.

Figure 12. Normalized Taylor diagram of proposed system compared to existing methods.

Figure 13. Scatter plots illustrating the Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) scores of the proposed system compared to state-of-the-art methods.